

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF A SWIRL-TYPE
BURNER CAP FOR DOMESTIC GAS GEYSERSMuhammad Ismail¹, Faiq Said², Zeeshan Khan³, Zarak Khan⁴, Salman Khan⁵,
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Domestic geyser; Swirl burner; slot angle; Combustion efficiency; Flue gas analysis

Article History

Received: 05 December 2025

Accepted: 20 January 2026

Published: 19 February 2026

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Abstract

Enhancing combustion efficiency in domestic gas geysers is essential for reducing fuel consumption and pollutant emissions. This study presents a comparative experimental investigation of a conventional swirl burner cap and a newly designed perforated 45° swirl-type burner cap for residential gas geysers. The modified burner cap was developed using a combined CAD-based design, sand casting, and CNC machining approach to ensure manufacturability and geometric precision. Performance evaluation was conducted on a domestic geyser test rig using real-time flue gas analysis and standardized combustion efficiency calculations. For the conventional swirl burner cap, the measured flue gas composition showed 8.40% O₂, 6.82% CO₂, and 0.0051% CO, with a stack temperature of 540.7 °C, resulting in a combustion efficiency of 68.41%. In contrast, the perforated swirl burner cap exhibited a significantly improved performance, with an average O₂ concentration of 11.80 ± 0.12%, reduced CO₂ concentration of 4.47 ± 0.40%, and CO emissions of 0.0045%. The stack temperature decreased substantially to 276.1 °C, indicating lower flue gas losses. Consequently, the modified burner achieved a higher average combustion efficiency of 82.03 ± 0.15%, representing an improvement of approximately 14% compared to the conventional design. The enhanced performance is attributed to improved air–fuel mixing and intensified turbulence generated by the hole-assisted swirl configuration. The results demonstrate that geometric modification of burner caps offers a simple, cost-effective solution for improving combustion efficiency and reducing emissions in domestic gas geysers. This study provides practical insights for the development of energy-efficient household heating appliances.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution continues to be a critical concern, primarily due to the persistent dependence on fossil fuels, which account for roughly 80 % of the global energy supply [1]. Addressing this issue, while meeting rising energy demands under

increasingly stringent environmental regulations, necessitates the development of cleaner and more sustainable combustion technologies [2]. One effective strategy is the transition toward gaseous fuels, which generally exhibit superior combustion

properties and produce significantly lower pollutant emissions compared to solid or liquid fuels [3]. Nevertheless, relying solely on gaseous fuels introduces operational challenges; their distinct flame characteristics can complicate system stability and require greater flexibility in combustor design [4].

Reducing energy consumption has emerged as a pressing global concern due to the depletion of fossil fuel reserves, economic limitations, and escalating environmental challenges [5,6]. Among energy carriers, natural gas has experienced the fastest consumption growth. As a technically reliable and economically viable fuel, natural gas remains widely used worldwide. In 2024, global natural gas consumption rose by 2.8 % relative to 2023, representing an additional 115 billion cubic meters (bcm) and contributing to approximately 40 % of the increase in global energy demand, with the Asia-Pacific region accounting for nearly 45 % of this growth [7,8]. Despite its widespread adoption, natural gas is non-renewable and associated with considerable carbon emissions, prompting several countries to implement regulations aimed at mitigating greenhouse gas emissions, particularly CO₂.

In Pakistan, natural gas consumption has grown at an average annual rate of 7.8 % over the last decade. As of December 2023, daily consumption reached 3.662 Bcf/d, slightly lower than 3.696 Bcf/d in 2022. During the fiscal year 2024 (July-March), total gas utilization averaged 3207 MMCFD, comprising 2512 MMCFD from natural gas and 695 MMCFD from re-gasified liquefied natural gas (RLNG). The power sector remains the largest consumer, followed by the residential sector [9]. A significant portion of this residential demand stems from household appliances such as domestic geysers; improving their combustion efficiency can reduce energy costs while contributing to national energy security and lowering emissions.

Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) has gained attention as a transitional fuel due to its availability, adaptability, and existing distribution infrastructure [10]. These attributes provide operational and logistical benefits that facilitate LPG integration into current industrial systems. In contrast, methane, although characterized by cleaner combustion and

lower greenhouse gas emissions, faces challenges in storage, transportation, and mitigation of fugitive emissions [11,12]. LPG's ease of handling and deployment positions it as a practical alternative for minimizing environmental impact while ensuring energy supply reliability [13].

Previous research on LPG-based domestic burners has demonstrated that key factors influencing performance include burner geometry, air-fuel mixing, and flame stabilization [14,15][15-17][16]. For instance, confinement ratio, slot configuration, and primary aeration have significant effects on flame stability, heat transfer, and pollutant emissions [16] [17]. Optimizing these parameters is essential to achieving higher thermal efficiency and lower CO and NO emissions in domestic appliances.

Swirl-type burners are widely recognized for their ability to improve combustion efficiency by promoting better air-fuel mixing and stable flame formation [14] [18,19] [20]. Swirl-induced recirculation zones enhance flame retention, increase residence time, and facilitate uniform heat distribution within the combustion zone. Studies on swirl burners indicate that geometric modifications, such as the incorporation of slots or holes, can further improve combustion performance, reducing flue gas losses and emissions while maintaining operational stability [20] [21].

Domestic LPG burners operate on principles analogous to conventional Bunsen burners, where combustion efficiency is primarily determined by primary aeration and jet velocity [22] [17]. However, overall burner performance is also affected by specific design parameters, including slot angle, cap geometry, and flow dynamics [23]. Standardized evaluation protocols, such as the Water Boiling Test (WBT, Shell Foundation), are commonly employed to assess efficiency, highlighting the influence of testing methodology on measured performance [24].

Research on domestic gas burners has largely focused on three interrelated aspects: (i) burner geometry and structural design, (ii) swirl flows and turbulence effects, and (iii) combustion emissions and energy efficiency. A systematic understanding of these factors provides the basis for improving domestic geyser performance and motivates the present study on comparative performance evaluation of swirl-type burner caps.

1.1 Burner Geometry and Structural Design

Burner geometry is a primary factor affecting combustion efficiency, flame characteristics, and heat transfer. Domestic LPG burners operate on principles similar to conventional Bunsen burners [22], where efficiency is largely influenced by primary aeration, jet velocity [17], and burner head design [23].

Prior research indicates that nozzle configuration, burner head shape, and heat recirculation significantly impact thermal performance [23]. Porous recirculating burners with exhaust gas recirculation have been shown to enhance efficiency by reducing heat losses [25]. Structural modifications, such as annular inserts, spill trays, and adjustments in loading height, further improve heat transfer and efficiency [26] [27]. Material selection also affects performance; for example, brass burners have been observed to outperform cast iron designs by approximately 4% in thermal efficiency [28] [29]. Additionally, interactions between the vessel and burner, including pot size and integrated fins, can provide measurable gains in heat transfer [30] [31]. Recently, an experimental evaluation of burner cap designs for residential gas geysers compared circular, plate, and swirl burners under controlled laboratory conditions [32]. The swirl burner exhibited superior performance, achieving peak thermal and combustion efficiencies of 54.1% and 75.2%, respectively, at a 49° cap angle. This improvement was attributed to enhanced turbulence and superior air-fuel mixing, which reduced CO emissions to as low as 27 ppm. In contrast, the plate and circular burners demonstrated lower efficiencies, confirming the dominant influence of burner geometry on combustion behavior. These findings highlight swirl-induced turbulence as a critical design parameter for improving domestic geyser performance.

Despite these advancements, most studies have concentrated on flat, porous, or hole-patterned burners, with limited investigation into cap tilt or swirl angles above 40°, restricting understanding of higher-intensity turbulence effects.

1.2 Swirl Flows and Turbulence Effects

Swirl flows are an effective mechanism for enhancing air-fuel mixing and stabilizing flames. Research has shown that swirl motion improves both efficiency

and emissions performance, though excessive swirl or elevated loading heights can reduce thermal efficiency due to higher atmospheric losses [33] [34,35]. Experimental comparisons of swirling strip-ported burners with conventional designs demonstrate reductions in NO_x formation under swirl conditions [36]. Increased swirl angles can enhance thermal performance but may also raise CO emissions if not carefully managed [36] [37].

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) studies have provided further insights into swirl behavior. Turbulent combustion modeling in self-aerated burners highlights the importance of uniform premixing for stability, while flame position and turbulence intensity strongly influence efficiency [38] [39]. Optimal flame delivery angles are generally in the 30°-35° range, with higher swirl and inclination angles (up to 60° and 30°, respectively) showing additional efficiency gains, albeit at the cost of increased CO formation [40,41]. Nevertheless, systematic experimental investigations of swirl angles above 40° in residential appliances remain limited, primarily due to fabrication and design constraints.

Complementing domestic-scale research, a novel counter-rotating double-swirl burner was recently developed for diesel-LPG cofiring [42]. Cold-flow simulations confirmed that the premix chamber created strong central and outer recirculation zones essential for flame stability. At a liquid-to-gas energy ratio of 70/30, the burner achieved a maximum thermal efficiency of 51%, a 40% reduction in flame length, and a 95% reduction in CO emissions compared to pure diesel operation. Although this study targeted industrial-scale combustion, it clearly demonstrates how swirl-induced recirculation zones enhance mixing, stabilize flames, and improve efficiency, principles that directly support swirl optimization strategies for domestic geyser applications.

1.3 Emissions and Environmental Considerations

Combustion efficiency alone does not ensure environmentally responsible operation; emissions of CO, NO_x, and CO₂ are equally important. Studies have shown that swirl burners significantly reduce CO emissions compared to conventional stoves [36] [35]. Structured baffle configurations in domestic gas geysers improve heat transfer, fuel-air mixing, and

reduce gas consumption. For example, bladed frustums achieved high thermal efficiency (69.03%) but slightly reduced combustion efficiency, while other frustum designs balanced efficiency (67.07%) with reduced fuel use [43]. Optimized flow structures and porous inserts can simultaneously enhance thermal performance and mitigate pollutant formation [44] [45] [44] [46].

Inclined burner geometries and higher swirl angles can lower CO₂ and NO_x emissions but often increase CO, reflecting the typical efficiency-emissions trade-off [40,41][47]. Studies incorporating hydrogen enrichment demonstrate extended lean burning limits and reduced CO formation [48]. Similarly, adjusting loading heights can decrease CO emissions while improving efficiency by approximately 20% [49]. Collectively, these findings indicate that emissions are strongly dependent on

swirl intensity, geometric configuration, and air-fuel ratios. However, the effects of higher swirl angles on the simultaneous control of CO, CO₂, and NO_x in residential appliances remain largely unexplored.

The recent domestic geyser burner study [32] further demonstrated that a 49° swirl cap produced the lowest emissions among tested configurations, particularly reducing unburned hydrocarbons and CO. This confirms that swirl geometry plays a decisive role in emission control for residential heating systems. Similarly, diesel-LPG cofiring in a double-swirl burner achieved ultra-low NO_x levels while dramatically reducing CO emissions, although moderate increases in NO were observed due to elevated flame temperatures [42]. These results reinforce the strong coupling between swirl intensity, combustion temperature, and emission formation.

Table 1. Summary of Studies on Burner Design and Performance

Study	Focus	Method	Findings	Limitation / Gap
2023 [23]	Burner geometry	Experimental	Nozzle and head design strongly affect efficiency	No swirl analysis
2002 [25]	Porous recirculating burner	Experimental	Heat recirculation improved efficiency	Not swirl-based
2014 [33]	Swirl cap	Experimental	Swirl improved efficiency & reduced emissions	Swirl < 40°
2018 [34,35,50]	Swirl configurations	Experimental	Counter-swirl reduced CO	Efficiency loss at high load
2019 [36]	Swirl strip-port	Experimental	Significant NO _x reduction	No tilt optimization
2016 [39] and 2017 [38]	Self-aerated burners	CFD	Uniform mixing improved stability	No high-angle validation
2013 and 2017 [40,41]	Port geometry	CFD	Optimum at 30°-35°	No strong swirl study
2022 [47]	Angled burner holes	Experimental	>10% efficiency increase	Moderate angles only
2025 [32]	Geyser burner caps	Experimental	49° swirl gave 54.1% thermal, 75.2% combustion, CO=27 ppm	Lab-scale only
2026 [42]	Double-swirl cofiring	CFD + Exp	51% efficiency, 95% CO reduction	Industrial burner
2022 [31]	Vessel-burner interaction	Experimental	Fins improved heat transfer	Vessel-focused

From the literature summarized in Table 1, three major research gaps are evident. First, while burner hole patterns, inserts, and materials have been optimized, systematic investigation of swirl angles exceeding 40° remains scarce. Second, although swirl is widely recognized as a mixing enhancement mechanism, experimental validation in residential appliances is limited due to manufacturing challenges. Third, most studies emphasize CO reduction or thermal efficiency, with limited balanced evaluation of CO_2 and NO_x under strong swirl regimes.

The recent domestic geyser study [32] confirms the importance of optimizing swirl angles, yet testing was conducted only under laboratory conditions with limited operational variability. Similarly, double-swirl cofiring research [42] demonstrated the benefits of recirculation zones but focused on industrial burners rather than household appliances.

Despite extensive research in industrial systems, few studies focus on swirl optimization for household gas geysers. Conventional domestic burners often lack geometric refinement, presenting an opportunity to enhance combustion efficiency while remaining compatible with existing appliances.

1.4 Novelty Statement

This investigation presents the design and experimental evaluation of a perforated 45° swirl-type burner cap for domestic gas geysers. A combined CAD-based design, sand casting, and CNC machining approach is employed to develop a manufacturable burner cap with controlled swirl features. The novelty lies in the hole-assisted swirl configuration that enhances air-fuel mixing while remaining fully compatible with existing geyser systems. A standardized experimental framework using real-time flue gas analysis is established for reliable performance comparison between conventional and modified burner caps.

2. Study approach

2.1. Burner Design and Fabrication

The burner cap was developed using a structured approach, as shown in Figure 1. The process involved CAD modeling of the burner geometry, followed by sand casting using cast iron. CNC machining was then applied to achieve accurate dimensions and slot features, resulting in the final finished burner cap ready for testing.

Figure 1. Methodology of burner cap

2.2 Burner Configuration

The burner configuration employed in this study is based on a conventional domestic water tank geyser system, modified to accommodate a swirl-type burner cap for performance evaluation. The existing burner assembly of the geyser was retained, while the

conventional burner cap was replaced with a newly designed swirl burner cap to ensure a fair comparative assessment under identical operating conditions. The burner cap geometry was developed using CAD modeling to achieve precise dimensional control and repeatability, as illustrated in Figure 2,

which presents the three-dimensional CAD design of the burner cap. A detailed cross-sectional view of the burner cap is shown in Figure 3, highlighting the internal geometry responsible for inducing swirl and promoting improved air-fuel mixing within the

combustion zone. This configuration allows stable flame formation while maintaining compatibility with standard domestic geyser burner assemblies.

Figure 2. CAD Design of Burner Cap

Figure 3. Burner cap cross-sectional view

2.3 Fabrication of Burner Cap

The swirl burner cap was manufactured using a sand-casting process with gray cast iron, selected for its high thermal stability, durability, and suitability for high-temperature combustion applications. Initially, a cast iron mold was prepared based on the finalized CAD design, and molten metal was poured into the sand mold to form the basic burner cap geometry. After solidification and cooling, the cast component was subjected to CNC machining to achieve accurate dimensions, uniform thickness, and precise

formation of the swirl slots and holes. This post-casting machining ensured consistency and repeatability across the fabricated component. **Figure 4** shows the existing swirl burner cap without holes, while **Figure 5** presents the newly fabricated burner cap with holes used in the experimental study, highlighting the geometric modifications introduced to enhance air-fuel mixing and combustion performance.

Figure 4. Existing Swirl burner Cap without holes

Figure 5. Newly fabricated burner cap with holes

2.4 Experimental Setup

The experimental study was conducted using a domestic gas geyser test rig, modified to allow the installation of the fabricated swirl burner cap. The setup included precise instrumentation to monitor water temperature, gas flow, and combustion parameters. A flue gas analyzer, shown in Figure 7,

was used to measure O_2 , CO_2 , CO , and other combustion gases in real time. Figure 6 provides an overview of the water tank geyser and the overall experimental methodology, ensuring controlled and reproducible testing conditions for all burner cap configurations.

Figure 6. Water Tank Geyser

Figure 7. Flue gas analyzer

2.5 Measurement Parameters

The study measured flue gas concentrations (O₂, CO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, HC) and temperature parameters, including inlet (T_i), outlet (T_o), and

temperature rise (ΔT), along with ambient and stack temperatures. Temperature measurements were recorded using a K-type thermocouple, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. K-type thermocouple

specific constants for accurate performance assessment.

2.6 Combustion Efficiency Calculation

Combustion efficiency was evaluated using Eq. (1) for flue loss and Eq. (2) for efficiency, applying fuel-

$$q_A = (T_s - T_a) \times \left(\frac{A_2}{(21 - O_2)} + B \right) \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Efficiency} = 100 - q_A \tag{2}$$

- q_A : flue loss
- T_s : flue gas temperature
- T_a : supply air temperature

- O_2 : measured volumetric oxygen concentration (%)
- A_2 and B : fuel-dependent constants (values based on fuel composition, see Table 1)

Table 2. values of A2 and B

Fuel type	A2	B
Natural Gas	0.66	0.009
Fuel Oil	0.68	0.007
Town Gas	0.63	0.011
Cooking oven gas	0.60	0.011
LPG	0.63	0.008

3. Results

3.1 Combustion Characteristics of 45° Swirl Burner

The combustion characteristics of the 45° swirl burner were evaluated by analyzing the flue gas composition, stack temperature, and excess air ratio. For the existing swirl burner cap without holes, as presented in Table 2, the measured O₂ concentration was 8.40%, CO at 0.0051%, CO₂ at

6.82%, NO at 0.0042%, NO₂ at 0.00031%, and HC at 0.035%. The stack temperature (T_s) was recorded at 540.7°C, and the ambient temperature (T_a) was 26°C. Using the flue gas analysis, the calculated combustion efficiency was 68.41%. These results indicate moderate combustion with incomplete air-fuel mixing, typical of a conventional swirl cap without modifications.

Table 3. Combustion Efficiency for Existing Swirl type burner without Holes

O ₂	8.40%	Γ	13.696
CO	0.0051%	ζ	22.071
NO	0.0042%	∞	82.985
NO ₂	0.00031%	Mf	109.71g
CO ₂	6.82%	Ma	3029.907g
HC	0.035%	FAR	0.03621
TS	540.7°C	q _A	31.59
T _a	26°C	Efficiency	68.41%
ν	6.8569		

In contrast, the newly fabricated burner cap with holes showed significant improvements, as summarized in Table 3. The average O₂ concentration increased to 11.80 ± 0.12%, while CO₂ decreased to 4.47 ± 0.40%, reflecting enhanced combustion completeness. CO levels averaged 45 ± 2.52 ppm, and the measured stack temperatures (T_i)

ranged around 276.1°C. The excess air ratio increased to 133%, demonstrating better air-fuel interaction. The flue gas measurements confirm that introducing holes into the swirl cap enhanced the mixing of gas and air, improved flame stability, and promoted more uniform heat distribution within the burner.

Table 4. Data of the newly fabricated Cap with holes

Reading	O ₂ (%)	CO ₂ (%)	CO (ppm)	Loss (%)	Efficiency (%)	XAir (%)	Ra	T _f (°C)	T _i (°C)	ΔT (°C)
1	11.72	4.9	43	19.45	81.9	136	0.000878	279.5	35.9	243.6
2	11.92	4.1	48	18.89	82.2	127	0.001171	269.4	35.6	233.8
3	11.71	4.4	45	19.46	82	136	0.001023	279.3	35.8	243.5
Average ± SD	11.80 ± 0.12	4.47 ± 0.40	45 ± 2.52	19.27 ± 0.32	82.03 ± 0.15	133	0.001024	276.1	35.8	240.3

3.2 Combustion Efficiency

The combustion efficiency, calculated using the flue gas method (Eq. 1 and Eq. 2), further highlights the performance difference between the two designs. The existing burner cap without holes achieved 68.41% efficiency, whereas the newly fabricated cap with holes reached an average efficiency of $82.03 \pm 0.15\%$. This improvement of nearly 14% is attributed to reduced flue gas losses, more complete oxidation of the fuel, and enhanced thermal transfer due to the swirl effect induced by the cap holes. The data also show that consistent performance was achieved across multiple trials, with low standard deviation, indicating high repeatability and reliability of the experimental setup.

Overall, the results clearly demonstrate that the 45° swirl burner cap with holes significantly improves combustion performance by increasing efficiency, optimizing flue gas composition, and ensuring better thermal management compared to the conventional design.

4. Conclusions

This study experimentally evaluated the performance of a newly designed perforated 45° swirl-type burner cap in comparison with a conventional swirl burner cap for domestic gas geysers. The investigation confirms that geometric modification through hole-assisted swirl generation significantly enhances combustion characteristics and overall system performance. The conventional burner cap exhibited a combustion efficiency of 68.41%, with flue gas parameters of 8.40% O_2 , 6.82% CO_2 , and 0.0051% CO , and a high stack temperature of $540.7^\circ C$, indicating substantial heat loss. In contrast, the modified burner cap achieved a markedly higher average combustion efficiency of $82.03 \pm 0.15\%$, representing an improvement of approximately 14%. The optimized design resulted in an increased O_2 concentration of $11.80 \pm 0.12\%$, reduced CO_2 concentration of $4.47 \pm 0.40\%$, and low CO emissions of 0.0045%. Additionally, the stack temperature decreased significantly to $276.1^\circ C$, confirming reduced flue gas losses and improved thermal utilization.

The enhanced performance is attributed to improved air-fuel mixing and intensified turbulence generated by the perforated swirl configuration, which

promotes more complete combustion and stable flame formation. The low standard deviation across repeated trials demonstrates excellent repeatability and reliability of the experimental framework. Overall, the proposed burner cap offers a simple, low-cost, and manufacturable solution for improving energy efficiency and emission performance in domestic gas geysers. The findings highlight the strong potential of swirl geometry optimization as an effective strategy for developing energy-efficient household heating systems and reducing environmental impact.

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